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Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This document provides a description of the software components of the Policy Management Framework Layer, and Policy Development Toolkit Layer.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
AT	Analytical Tool
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
PM	Policy Model
PME	Policy Modelling Editor
PP	Public Policy
SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
UI	User Interface
UX	User eXperience
UML	Unified Modelling Language
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document is an incremental update of deliverable D5.3 Cross-sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Software Prototype 1, delivered in November 2020, and describes in detail the software components of the Policy Management Framework Layer and Policy Development Toolkit Layer, which are the frontend parts of the PolicyCLOUD platform and allow policy makers to create, update and evaluate policies. For each component, a description of its APIs, specification of the main functionalities, and description of the source code are provided.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This document is the second iteration of “Cross-Sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Software prototype”, and covers tasks T5.2, T5.3, T5.4, T5.5 and T5.6. Its main purpose is to provide a description of the prototype implementation of the Policy Modelling Editor (PME) and the Policy Development Toolkit (PDT) to support policy makers in the modelling, creation, update, and evaluation of the policies.

This document is consistent with deliverable D5.4 “Cross-Sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Design and Open Specification 2” [1], delivered in August 2021, which provided the overall architecture and design specifications of the PME and PDT.

This report will be further updated during the last phase of the project duration (at month M34, October 2022) and will include further advancements and contributions from other tasks.

1.2 Summary of changes

The main changes in this deliverable regard the update of Section 2.1 and 2.2. In this second version of the demonstrator, all components have been integrated and are running on the testbed infrastructure. Furthermore, integration work has been performed for the Maggioli and Sarga use cases, which are now integrated with the Policy Development Toolkit layer.

In addition, we have updated and revised the whole document (including figures) to reflect the current work done at M22 (October 2021).

1.3 Structure of the Deliverable

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the main components and sub-systems, their interfaces and technologies used for their development.
- Section 3 describes where the source code is made available.
- Finally, Section 4 provides the conclusion of the document.

2 Prototype overview

In this section we provide the description of the prototype implementation of the Policy Modelling Framework Layer and Policy Development Toolkit Layer, as illustrated in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 - POLICYCLOUD SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

2.1 Main components of the prototype

2.1.1 Policy Modelling Editor

The Policy Model Editor (PME) is the core component that supports and guides the end-user to effectively create a Policy Model safely. More specifically, the PME is a Single Page Application that relies on the PDT backend REST API to fetch or store related entities of the Policy Model.

2.1.2 Policy Development Toolkit

As described in the deliverable D2.2 “Conceptual Model and Reference Architecture”[2], PDT interacts with components from Layer 3 - Policies Management Framework (T5.1, T5.2), Analytical Tools (WP4) and the PDT Backend.

PDT provides the integrated prototype of the following components as described in the deliverable D5.4 “Cross-sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Design and Open Specification 2” [1]:

- Policy Model Viewer
- Policy Evaluations / Analytics

Integration with the Backend has been implemented, utilising Docker images. This way, PDT can retrieve default policy models in the structured JSON format which represent the Policy Models (PMs). So, the functionalities included in this prototype are:

- The policy maker can obtain a list of available policies and select one for further exploration,
- Once a policy is selected, the properties of the policy are shown, along with the available KPIs of the policy,
- Once a KPI is selected, the relative KPI properties are also shown to the user,
- The Analytical Tools (ATs) which can compute the selected KPI are presented. The policy maker can see the parameters related with each AT and invoke the respective AT. Finally, the policy maker can see a short overview of the current selected PMs.

The aforementioned functionalities are implemented as a policy wizard component, comprised by three steps.

The relative UI components are described in Section 2.2.2.

2.1.3 Data Visualization

The Data Visualization component has been successfully integrated with the PDT. This second prototype includes all graphs defined in the first prototype and now can be seen through the PDT. They are:

- A Heatmap as requested by the “Participatory Policies Against Radicalization” Use Case of Maggioli. This chart uses data extracted from the Data Analytics of WP4.

FIGURE 2 - EXAMPLE OF THE HEATMAP FOR MAGGIOLI USE CASE (EVENT LOCATOR)

This Heatmap is intended to show, at a glance, all incidents that occurred in a chosen region. Currently, there are two possible regions: “North America” and “Eastern Europe”; but the list will be enlarged in final version. Whenever a region is selected, the heatmap shows all incidents that took place in it. It can be filtered by location and by year, and it is possible to see the incident details, when clicking on it. Users can change regions as desired. The heat map can also show “hot” zones (zones with a bigger number of incidents) using colours, instead of numbers:

FIGURE 3 – EXAMPLE OF HEATMAP FOR MAGGIOLI USE CASE (“HOT” ZONES)

- A Line and Gauge charts as requested by the “Intelligent Policies for Denomination of Origin” Use Case of Sarga, that plots the evaluation of the Sentimental Analysis considering some Keywords.

FIGURE 4 - EXAMPLE OF THE LINE AND GAUGE CHARTS FOR THE SARGA USE CASE

Considering a set of keywords, the Sentiment Analysis Line chart shows the sentiments for these keywords during a given period. The Accumulated Sentiment Gauge chart shows the average of these sentiments, during the same period.

In order to achieve the internal milestone of having at least one chart by Use Case scenario, the visualization component has been incremented and has integrated other charts. They are:

- A heatmap, requested by the “Facilitating urban policy making and monitoring through crowdsourcing data analysis” Use Case of Sofia. In this case, an adaptation of previous Heatmap has been done, following Sofia Use Case’s requirements. In this way, the adapted Heatmap is focused on Sofia city and can filter by Sofia’s districts, by year, and, also, differently from Maggioli Use Case, by months and days.

FIGURE 5 - EXAMPLE OF THE HEATMAP FOR THE SOFIA USE CASE

- A Bar Chart, required both for Sofia and London Use Cases. In the case of London, it is intended to show unemployment data by gender:

Name: number of claiming by gender (in colours) and per year/month (x-axes)
Dataset: Claimants
Range: 01Jan2021 - 31Dic2021

Filter by:

Show as Stacked

FIGURE 6 - EXAMPLE OF THE BAR CHART FOR THE LONDON USE CASE

And for Sofia, the chart represents the number of incidents per month and per district (the 24 districts of Sofia):

Name: num of incidents per month(x-axes) and per district (y-axes)
Dataset: road infrastructure
Range: 01Jan2021 - 31Dic2021

Filter by:

Show as Cluster

FIGURE 7 - EXAMPLE OF BAR CHART FOR THE SOFIA USE CASE

Both are the same Bar charts, with different data, but that can be seen in two different formats: cluster and stacked.

Also, for Sofia Use Case, there's another Bar Chart, where the data that can be visualized is the number of incidents by subcategories per districts:

FIGURE 8 - EXAMPLE OF ANOTHER BAR CHART FOR THE SOFIA USE CASE

2.1.4 PDT Backend

The PDT backend provides support to the whole PDT, and can be considered as the layer between the user interfaces that the policy maker can use to have access the tool, the policy modelling editor, and the *Data Acquisition and Analytics* layer of the PolicyCLOUD platform, provided by the components of WP4 and WP3. It exposes its functionality via REST APIs and web sockets, to allow for the integration with the aforementioned components, while it also makes use of the REST API provided by the *Data Acquisition and Analytics* layer. As a result, it serves four main purposes:

- Allows storing, modifying and retrieving *policies*, along with their relevant corresponding entities (i.e., KPIs, stakeholders, etc.)
- Hold policy meta-information that can be used by the policy modelling editor, in order for the latter to propose new policies to the domain experts
- Invoke an analytical tool to perform an analysis through the *Data Acquisition and Analytics* layer, given the input parameters defined by the KPIs of the involved policy
- Allow for the retrieval of the results of the analytical tools, which can be later fed to the visualization component of the tool. This involves again the integration of the backend with the *Data Acquisition and Analytics* layer

More precisely, regarding the functionality implemented at this phase of the project for the PDT and the Policy Model Editor, the backend provides the ability to:

- Store, and retrieve *actors*, based on their name or the domain they are related to
- Retrieve information about the Analytical Tools that are available in the *Data Acquisition and Analytic* layer. Those tools can be retrieved either by name, by the domain they are related to or according to the datasets that they are compatible with

- Retrieve information about the available datasets, stored in the central data repository of PolicyCLOUD and managed by the *Data Acquisition and Analytic* layer
- Add, remove, modify and retrieve domains that can be relevant to the entities of the *policies*
- Add, remove, modify and retrieve goals of a *KPI*, and associate those tools with stakeholders
- Check the status of a *job*, which has been submitted as the result of the invocation of an analytical tool
- Get information about a *job*, submitted by the invocation of an analytical tool
- Get the result of an analysis, related to its *job*
- Add, remove, modify and retrieve *KPIs*, based on their name, their corresponding domain or their relevant actors
- Add or remove actors, goals, domains and data models from a *KPI*
- Add, remove, modify and retrieve policies, according to their names, the user that stored the policy or their corresponding domain they belong to.
- Add or remove *KPIs* from *policies*
- Store combined types of results of analytical tools, thus giving the opportunity to the end-user to switch between different views of the same results
- Correlate policies with the end-users that have defined them
- Retrieve policies depending on the user that has issued the request
- Correlate *jobs* with the users that initially submitted a request to execute an analysis
- Retrieve the results of the *jobs* owned by a given end-users
- Cancel the execution of an analysis if it exceeds the defined maximum response time allowed
- Provides a warning when the result of an analysis exceeds the maximum number of characters that can be efficiently processed by the visualization tools at a later phase

Regarding the interaction with the *Data Acquisition and Analytic* layer, the corresponding APIs have been defined in deliverable D4.4. The Backend of the PDT is integrated with the latter, in order to implement the higher-level functionality, as described above.

The backend of the PDT consists of a single process that runs on a servlet container. It relies on a relational datastore to store the relational model of the policy, its attributes, related entities, and relations between them. It should be highlighted that the datastore which is being used by this component is not the central data repository of PolicyCLOUD, as it is used for storing the raw data coming from the data providers, along with the results of the analytical tools. The purpose of the data storage element of this component is to store the policies and the metadata information that are related with those, along with the results of the analytical tools, while at the same time it aims at providing a standard way for communicating with the backend.

2.2 Interfaces

2.2.1 Policy Modelling Editor

Upon the end-user’s entrance into the PME, the end-user has to both indicate the domain of its Policy Model and to provide a short description. Furthermore, the end-user has to provide to the PME the existing KPIs that might fit in the Policy Model under consideration.

Figure 9 illustrates the Home Page interface of the PME. It fetches from the PDT backend KPIs that belong in the same domain with the Policy Model; and then prompted by the component to continue in the next page to select existing KPIs.

FIGURE 9 - POLCIY MODEL EDITOR HOME PAGE

Figure 10 shows the Existing KPIs selection interface, in which the end-user has the capability to add or to select existing Actors that are included in the Policy Model domain.

FIGURE 10 - EXISTING KPIS SELECTION

In the Add new KPI interface (see Figure 11) the end-user has the capability to create a new KPI; while he/she can enter the relevant info of the KPI, describe its Goals, and integrate the additional Stakeholders.

FIGURE 11 - ADD NEW KPI

It should be noted that the user has the following capabilities: (i) to provide description of the Data Model and add or select Actors, (ii) to select the relevant Analytical Tools from a specific list (drop-down menu) (Figure 12), (iii) to provide the parameter values that comes for the Analytical Tools (Figure 13), (iv) to review and submit the Policy Model (Figure 14).

Create new Key Performance Indicators

+ ADD NEW KPI

KPI Info

Info *

KPI Info

Provide information about the KPI

Formula

Enter KPI formula if any

Data

Goal **Actors** KPI Elements

Select Actor to add + ADD SELECTED ACTOR

+ ADD NEW ACTOR

Actor Name *	Select Domain *
actor1	SECURITY, AGRIFOOD
new actor	SECURITY, ROAD_INFRASTRUCTURE

localhost:4200

FIGURE 12 - ADD NEW ACTOR

Data

Goal Actors **KPI Elements**

+ ADD ELEMENT

KPI Element #1

Name *

Name

Name the model

Info Php

Provide information about the Data Model (optional) Data (optional)

Analytical Tool

name1 Graph Created At

name2 chart 2020-11-11, Wed, 08:57:53 GMT

name3

Parameters

param_name

info1

Go back to Search and select existing Key Performance Indicators Preview and submit the Policy

PREVIOUS NEXT

FIGURE 13 - ANALYTICAL TOOL SELECTION

FIGURE 14 - SET PARAMETER VALUE

Finally, if the process was successful the user is redirected to the last page that promotes the user to visit the PDT and evaluate the submitted Policy Model or compose a new one.

FIGURE 15 - REVIEW AND SUBMIT

FIGURE 16 - POLICY MODEL SUBMITTED

2.2.2 Policy Development Toolkit

The following figures present the UI implementations of the PDT functionalities, as listed in Section 2.1.2. The web pages are served locally communicating with the dockerised backend API.

Figure 17 shows the landing web page of PDT (after the pending Authentication procedure). The page shows the three-step policy wizard, with the first step as the default location. Here the user selects a policy from a list of available policy models.

FIGURE 17 – POLICY SELECTION-EVALUATION WIZARD

Figure 18 shows the properties of the policy model selected by the user. After the selection of a policy, the related KPIs are displayed, and the PM can select one KPI for evaluation.

FIGURE 18 - POLICY SELECTION AND POLICY PROPERTIES

Figure 18 displays the step for the KPI selection and Figure 19 shows the properties of the selected KPI, e.g., formula, data, domain, goal, actors and stakeholders.

- 1 Policy Model
- 2 **Key Performance Indicator**
- 3 Evaluation-Analytics
- 4 Policy Summary

Select a Key Performance Indicator of the chosen Policy ()

Select KPI *

Next

FIGURE 19 - KPI SELECIION

KPI info1

ID
1

Info
info1

Formula
formula1

Data
data1

Domain
SECURITY

Goal ID
1

Goal
goalinfo

Stakeholders

Actors
actor1 actor2

FIGURE 20 – KPI PROPERTIES

Figure 21 shows the third step of the wizard, which is the evaluation of the selected KPI, by using the proper Analytics Tool.

FIGURE 21 – EVALUATION – ANALYTICS TOOL SELECTION

Figure 22 shows technical details of the Analytics Tool in an expandable card, as to not distract the PM.

FIGURE 22 – ANALYTICS TOOL TECHNICAL DETAILS

Figure 23 shows the parameter list that the selected Analytics Tool is expecting for invocation. A parameter's values overview is also presented, which includes the default values for the calculation of the KPI.

Parameters

param_name

Description
param_description

Unit
MONTHS

Parameter info ▼

Parameter Value:

Value(s)
JULY

Analytic Tool Parameter Values:

Parameter Name	Value(s)
param_name	JULY

A name for this submission

A description for this submission

Run the Analytics

FIGURE 23 – ANALYTICS TOOL PARAMETERS & SUBMISSION

Figure 24 shows the details for each parameter of the Analytical tool, also in the form of an expandable card.

Parameter info

ID	Parameter Name
77ac4062-4c15-4f15-9355-2	param_name
Value Type	Evaluation Type
STRING	EQUAL
Input Type	Required Value
VARIABLE	true

Parameter Constraints:

DEFAULT

default value

FIGURE 24 – ANALYTICS TOOL PARAMETERS DETAILS

Figure 25 shows the fourth step of the wizard, presenting a short overview of the selected policy.

1 Policy Model — 2 Key Performance Indicator — 3 Evaluation-Analytics — 4 Policy Summary

Current Policy Overview

PP: policySname1
Owner: Error Occured!

KPI(s): info1 (data1)

Back

FIGURE 25 – POLICY OVERVIEW / SAVING

Figure 26 shows the UI Menu for selecting different PDT components.

FIGURE 26 – PDT COMPONENTS MENU

For each step of the wizard help menu is available. Figure 27 shows the online help for the 1st step of the wizard.

FIGURE 27 - ONLINE HELP

At the footnote of each PDT page, the link for the End Users Data Protection Information has been added, as shown in Figure 28 and Figure 29.

FIGURE 28 - USER DATA PROTECTION INFORMATION NOTICE

FIGURE 29 - USER DATA PROTECTION TEXT

A user-friendly guide / FAQ on how PolicyCLOUD users should address each parameter required from them for the registration (in particular, those specified in order to ensure legal/ethical compliance) is being developed as part of the implementation of the WP4 Legal/Ethical Checklist.

After the authentication of the User by providing his/her credentials to the Authentication server, the User Profile is available to the PDT page. Figure 30 shows the User Profile, as well as the Logout action button.

FIGURE 30 - USER PROFILE PROPERTIES / LOGOUT

2.2.3 Data Visualization

From the initial page, users will select the different options offered by the tool, and among them, the graphics to visualize the results of the selected analytics.

When a HeatMap is selected to visualize the analytics results, depending on the Use Case, it will receive the data in one or another format. These data format has been changed to respect the initial prototype of the Visualization Tool, but has been also agreed with WP4, and contain data for both, Maggioli and Sofia Use Cases. The json is like:

```

{"level": "city",
 "id": 2,
 "typeOfCharts": "HEATMAP_POI",
 "name": "Sofia",
 "location":
  {"type": "Point",
   "coordinates": [23.329334, 42.719941]},
   "data": {
     "events": [
       {
         "eventid": 233126,
         "timestamp": 1607261844007,
         "latitude": "42.706235908163251",
         "longitude": "23.147978751984407",
         "iyear": 2020,
         "imonth": 12,
         "iday": 6,
         "esummary": "Aquí ira la descripcion detallada del incidente"
       }
     ]
   }
 }

```

FIGURE 31 - EXAMPLE FOR HEAT MAP CHART DATA

Where data field is the data returned by the Analytics Tool, and the other fields are added by the PDT Backend, which is the one that does the communication between Analytics and the Visualization. The input data used for Sarga Use Case has been provided by the Sentimental Analysis component from WP4, and the agreed format is:

```

{
  "id":1,
  "data":{"acc_sentiment":0.23,"keywords":"TBD","list_sentiment":[],"title":"Sentiment"}\n",
  "typeOfCharts":"GAUGE"
}

```

FIGURE 32 – EXAMPLE FOR SARGA GAUGE CHART DATA

In the case of the Bar chart for London Use Case, the data received has the format:

```

{
  "id":14,
  "data": {"filterToUse":"year","filterValues":[2020,2021],"range_date":["01Jan2021","31Dic2021"],
    "x-axes":"year/month","y-axes":"number of claiming","name":"number of claiming by gender (in col)",
    "dataset":"Claimants","descripcion":"N": {"descripcion":"","value":0},
    "data":[{"category":"2020 January","year":"2020","male":40,"female":20,"total":60},
    {"category":"2020 February","year":"2020","male":5,"female":55,"total":67}]}",
  "typeOfCharts":"CLUSTEREDCOLUMNCHART"
}

```

FIGURE 33 – EXAMPLE FOR LONDON BAR CHART DATA

In the case of Sofia's Bar charts, the data received has the format:

```
{
  "id":14,
  "data": [{"filterToUse":"year","filterValues":[2020,2021],"range_date":["01Jan2021","31Dic2021"],
    "x-axes":"months","y-axes":"incidents","name":"num of incidents per month(x-axes) and per distri",
    "dataset":"road infrastructure","descripcion":"","N":{"descripcion":"Reduce to the most N rep",
    "value":3},"data":[{"category":"2020 January","year":"2020","District 1":40,"District 2":20,
    "District 3": 60},{"category":"2020 February","year":"2020","District 1":5,"District 2":55,
    "District 3": 67}]}],
  "typeOfCharts":"CLUSTEREDCOLUMNCHART"
}
```

FIGURE 34 – EXAMPLE FOR ONE BAR DATA FOR SOFIA

2.2.4 PDT Backend

As described in the previous subsection, the backend of the PDT exposes its interfaces via a REST API. In order to provide an always up-to-date documentation of the definition of the interface to the developers of other components, we automated this process by making use of the swagger [3] open source documentation UI. Swagger allows the developer to annotate her source code and provides tools and plugins that auto-generate the documentation during compilation time. It generates JSON files with all the relevant information. It also provides a web application that can be used as the UI tool for the consumer of the REST services to see their documentation. This web application makes use of those auto-generated JSON files to build the user interface. Moreover, it provides to the REST service consumer the ability to test the interface online, by invoking them in real-time and check the results.

The following code snippet indicates how the developer of a REST service can annotate the latter via the swagger framework.

```
@Path("/domains")
@Api(basePath="http://localhost:54735/pdt", value = "/domains", description = "REST Service that
provides functionalities for domains")
public class DomainResource {
```

The class *DomainResource* implements the web methods related with the functionalities for the *domains*, and it has been annotated to use the REST path */domains*. As it can be noted, the developer can additionally annotate the class with the *@Api* that informs the swagger that this REST resource should be documented.

Moreover, at the level of web methods, the following code snippet shows how the developer can document the details of each invocation

```
@GET
@Path("/starts")
@ApiOperation(value="Returns the list of domains that starts with the given input",
notes="Returns the list of domains that starts with the given input",
responseContainer = "List", response = DomainDTOImpl.class)
@ApiResponses(value= {
  @ApiResponse(code=500, message="Exception's message")
})
@Produces(MediaType.APPLICATION_JSON)
```

```
@SuppressWarnings("UseSpecificCatch")
public Response getDomainsStartingWith(
    @ApiParam(value = "the start with parameter", required = true)
    @QueryParam("name") String name) {
```

This web method that returns all *domains* whose name starts with a given value. The swagger annotation indicates to the framework that this should be an operation that will return a *List* of serialized objects of the *DomainDTOImpl* class. Besides the default HTTP code 200 that indicates a successful invocation, this web method can also return an HTTP error code 500 and provides the parameter that is required. Swagger, uses Java Reflection to retrieve additional information like the type of the invocation (GET, POST, PUT etc.) the name and type of the input parameters, the media type used in the body of the request or/and the response of the HTTP call etc.

Finally, the DTOs that will be transferred via the REST calls, can also be annotated, as the following code snippet indicates.

```
@JsonIgnoreProperties(ignoreUnknown = true)
public class DomainDTOImpl implements DomainDTO, Serializable {
    private static final long serialVersionUID = 1L;

    @ApiModelProperty(value="domain id", required=true)
    private Long id;
    @ApiModelProperty(value="domain name", required=true)
    private String name;

    @JsonCreator
    public DomainDTOImpl(
        @JsonProperty("id") Long id,
        @JsonProperty("name") String name) {
        this.id = id;
        this.name = name;
    }
}
```

The aforementioned *DomainDTOImpl* used by the web method explained before, has two attributes, the *id* and the *name* of the domain. The *ApiModelProperty* can be used by swagger to provide this kind of information to the documentation.

After having annotated all our web services, web methods and DTOs, the swagger plugin for maven was used to auto-generate the stub information in JSON files. The following code snippet was used to do this work.

```
<plugin>
  <groupId>com.github.kongchen</groupId>
  <artifactId>swagger-maven-plugin</artifactId>
  <version>2.3.4</version>
  <configuration>
    <apiSources>
      <apiSource>
        <locations>eu.policycloud.rest.resources</locations>
        <apiVersion>${project.version}</apiVersion>
        <basePath>/resources</basePath>
      </apiSource>
    </apiSources>
  </configuration>
</plugin>
```

```

<swaggerDirectory>${project.basedir}/src/main/webapp/</swaggerDirectory>

<outputTemplate>${project.basedir}/src/main/resources/markdown.mustache</outputTemplate>

<mustacheFileRoot>${project.basedir}/src/main/resources/</mustacheFileRoot>

<outputPath>${project.basedir}/src/main/webapp/document.html</outputPath>
  </apiSource>
</apiSources>
</configuration>
<executions>
  <execution>
    <phase>compile</phase>
    <goals>
      <goal>generate</goal>
    </goals>
  </execution>
</executions>
</plugin>

```

It creates the JSON files during *compile phase*, and adds them to corresponding directory where the swagger app is expecting to retrieve this information, while it also modifies the markdown mustache template used by the web app.

After setting up everything, the online documentation is now available. The following screenshots show this documentation per REST Web Service implemented.

actors		Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations
GET	/actors/starts	Returns the list of actors that starts with the given input
GET	/actors/{id}/remove	removes a domain from an actor
DELETE	/actors	removes an actor
GET	/actors	Returns the full list of actors
GET	/actors/add	Adds a new actor
DELETE	/actors/{id}	removes an actor
GET	/actors/{id}	Returns an actor based on its id
GET	/actors/name	Returns an actor based on its name
GET	/actors/{id}/add	Adds a domain to an actor
GET	/actors/domain/{domain}	Returns the full list of actors related with a domain
GET	/actors/test	Testing operation

FIGURE 35 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH ACTORS

analytical.tool Show/Hide | List Operations | Expand Operations

DELETE	/analytical.tool/{id}	removes a tool
GET	/analytical.tool/{id}	Returns a service analysis based on its id
GET	/analytical.tool	Returns the full list of available analytical tools
POST	/analytical.tool	Adds a new tool
PUT	/analytical.tool	Updates a tool
GET	/analytical.tool/domain/{domain}	Returns the full list of available analytical tools related with a policy
GET	/analytical.tool/datamodel/{datamodel}	Returns the full list of available analytical tools related with a datamodel
GET	/analytical.tool/test	Testing operation

FIGURE 36 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH ANALYTICAL TOOLS

data.models Show/Hide | List Operations | Expand Operations

GET	/data.models	Returns the full list of all data models
POST	/data.models	Adds a data model
PUT	/data.models	Updates a data model
GET	/data.models/{id}	Returns a data model based on its id
GET	/data.models/name	Returns a data model based on its name
GET	/data.models/test	Testing operation

FIGURE 37 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH DATA MODELS

domains Show/Hide | List Operations | Expand Operations

GET	/domains/add	Adds a new domain
GET	/domains	Returns the full list of actors
GET	/domains/name	Returns a domain based on its name
GET	/domains/{id}	Returns an domain based on its id
GET	/domains/starts	Returns the list of domains that starts with the given input
GET	/domains/test	Testing operation

FIGURE 38 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH DOMAINS

goals Show/Hide | List Operations | Expand Operations

DELETE	/goals/{id}	removes a goal
GET	/goals/{id}	Returns a goal based on its id
GET	/goals	Returns the full list of goals
POST	/goals	Adds a goal
PUT	/goals	Updates a goal
GET	/goals/stakeholder/{stakeholder}	Returns the full list of goals that belong to a stakeholder
GET	/goals/{id}/add	Adds a stakeholder to a goal based on its id
GET	/goals/{id}/remove	Removes a stakeholder from a goal based on its id
GET	/goals/test	Testing operation

FIGURE 39 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH GOALS

job.status Show/Hide | List Operations | Expand Operations

GET	/job.status/types	Returns the full list of allowed job statuses
GET	/job.status	Returns all statuses
PUT	/job.status	Updates a job status
DELETE	/job.status/{id}	removes a job status
GET	/job.status/{id}	Returns a status based on its id
POST	/job.status/job/{id}	Adds a new job status to an existing job
GET	/job.status/test	Testing operation

FIGURE 40 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH JOB STATUS

jobs

Show/Hide | List Operations | Expand Operations

DELETE	/jobs/{id}	removes a job
GET	/jobs/{id}	Returns a job based on its id
POST	/jobs/{id}	Adds a result to a job
GET	/jobs	Returns all submitted jobs
POST	/jobs	Adds a new job
PUT	/jobs	Updates a job
GET	/jobs/{id}/result	Returns a result of a job based on its id
GET	/jobs/analytical.tool/{id}	Returns all submitted jobs of an analytical service
GET	/jobs/{id}/status	Returns the status of a job based on its id
GET	/jobs/admin/{id}	Returns the jobs of a admin based on her id
GET	/jobs/test	Testing operation

FIGURE 41 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH JOBS

kpis

Show/Hide | List Operations | Expand Operations

DELETE	/kpis/{id}	removes a kpi
GET	/kpis/{id}	Returns a kpi based on its id
GET	/kpis/goal/{goal}	Returns the full list of kpis by a goal
GET	/kpis	Returns the full list of kpis
POST	/kpis	Adds a kpi
PUT	/kpis	Updates a kpi
GET	/kpis/domain/{domain}	Returns the full list of kpis by a domain
GET	/kpis/actor/{actor}	Returns the full list of kpis by an actor
POST	/kpis/{id}/add.goal	adds a new goal to a kpi
GET	/kpis/{id}/add.actor	Adds an actor to a kpi based on its id
GET	/kpis/{id}/remove.actor	Removes an actor from a kpi based on its id
POST	/kpis/{id}/add.data.model/{datamodelid}	Adds a data model to a kpi.
POST	/kpis/{id}/remove.data.model	Removes a data model from a kpi.
GET	/kpis/test	Testing operation

FIGURE 42 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH KPIS

policies		Show/Hide	List Operations	Expand Operations
GET	/policies			Returns the full list of policies
POST	/policies			Adds a policy
PUT	/policies			Updates a policy
POST	/policies/insert			Adds a policy
POST	/policies/{id}/remove.kpi			Removes a kpi from a policy.
POST	/policies/{id}/add.kpi			Adds a kpi to a policy.
DELETE	/policies/{id}			removes a policy
GET	/policies/{id}			Returns a policy based on its id
GET	/policies/admin/{id}			Returns the policies of a policy admin based on her id
GET	/policies/domain/{domain}			Returns the policies related with a domain
GET	/policies/admin/default			Returns the default policies
GET	/policies/name			Returns a policy based on its name
GET	/policies/test			Testing operation
POST	/policies/test			Testing operation

FIGURE 43 - WEB METHODS RELATED WITH POLICIES

Finally, the Backend allows for asynchronous communication with the PDT via web sockets. This is crucial when other components perform updates that the Backend should be aware of, so that the PDT can modify the UI in order to reflect those updates, without having to continuously invoke the Backend to ask for potential pending updates. This helps to improve the overall UX of the end-user. For instance, when an analytical tool finishes its executions and produces some results, the *Data Acquisition and Analytic* API notifies the Backend, which will be triggered in order to send a message via this web socket to the PDT. By doing this, the PDT can be in position to update the status of a pending job, without periodically ask this status from the backend. The DTOs that are exchanged have the following format:

```
{
  "id": 3242,
  "notification": "UPDATED",
  "job": {
    "id": 3242,
    "name": "job name",
    "description": "the description of the job",
    "status": "FINISHED",
    "dateCreated": "2021-10-01T09:23:43"
    .
    .
    .
  }
}
```

In this DTO, the *id* is the unique identifier of the *job* its status has been changed and the *notification* can accept one of the following values: ADDED, UPDATED or DELETED. Finally, the *job* contains all information about the corresponding *job*, like its *id*, *name*, *description*, *status*, etc.

2.3 Baseline technologies and tools

2.3.1 Policy Modelling Editor

As described in the deliverable D5.4 “Cross-sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Design and Open Specification 2”[1], the PME is developed using the open-source Angular framework [4]. For UI components and controls we use the Angular Material library [5].

2.3.2 Policy Development Toolkit

As described in the deliverable D5.2 “Cross-sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Design and Open Specification 1” Section 4.2, PDT is built as a Single Page Application developed using the open-source Angular framework [4][3]. For UI components and controls we use the Angular Material library [5].

The PDT is using Docker to encapsulate the web serving functionality along with NGINX [6] web server.

2.3.3 Data Visualization

As the Data Visualization is part of the PDT, it has been developed using the same base technology, AngularJS v10 [4]. The main JavaScript libraries used for this first prototype are:

- Leaflet [7] is used to plot the heatmap
- Amcharts [8] is used to plot the line and the gauge charts

Although the component is integrated into the PDT, a standalone version can also be used, and the detailed invocation instructions are detailed into the readme file that accompanies the source code of the component. Still, the service can be started either with a NodeJS server or using a Docker container (see Section 3.1.3).

To visualize it as part of the PDT, this component has to be started and all previous steps must be taken.

2.3.4 PDT Backend

The backend of PDT has been implemented using Java SDK 8. It does not make use of any framework like Spring, but it relies on the standard JDK. For the implementation of the REST services, it makes use of the javax servlet API 3.1.0 while it also makes use of an embedded tomcat, as the servlet container that the web services are deployed. We rely on the Apache Embedded Tomcat 8 [9]. By doing this, there is no need to maintain an additional standalone container like Tomcat, Glassfish or similar, rather than the java virtual machine starts the embedded one inside its process. Moreover, Maven 3 was used as the tool for the automation of the build process. For the persistent storage of this component, we relied on the LXS relational datastore. However, this is not mandatory and therefore, the Backend component of the PDT can switch to other relational datastore, with minimal changes in the source code.

3 Source Code

3.1 Availability

3.1.1 Policy Modelling Editor

The source code of the prototype of the Policy Modelling Editor component is available at:

- Project GitLab repository: <http://snf-877903.vm.okeanos.grnet.gr/chris/policy-model-editor>

3.1.2 Policy Development Toolkit

The source code of the prototype of the Policy Development Toolkit component is available at:

- Project GitLab repository: <http://snf-877903.vm.okeanos.grnet.gr/kostas/pdt>

3.1.3 Data Visualization

The source code of the Data Visualization component is available separately at:

- Project GitLab repository: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/ana.pontual/visualization>

Or through the PDT at:

- Project GitLab repository: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/kostas/pdt>

3.1.4 PDT Backend

The Backend of the PDT is currently released under open source license, and its source code has been uploaded and is publicly available at:

- Project GitLab repository: https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/pdt-backend

It also provides the tools to compile the source code and also build a docker image that can deploy and run this component.

As already mentioned, the PDT Backend requires the use of a relational data store to persistently store its policies, policy related meta-information and results of the analytical tools. We relied on the datastore provided by LXS, which can be found at:

- Project GitLab repository: https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/policy-store

As the datastore is published with LXS IPR licence, its source code cannot be available. However, the GitLab repositories for the datastore contains all binaries and scripting files necessary for packaging the distribution and creating a docker container that the datastore can start within.

3.2 Deployment

3.2.1 Policy Modelling Editor

The Policy Modelling Editor will follow the Cloud provider setups and Kubernetes staging.

3.2.2 Policy Development Toolkit

The Policy Development Toolkit will follow the Cloud provider setups and Kubernetes staging.

3.2.3 Data Visualization

The Data Visualization will follow the Cloud provider setups and Kubernetes staging. Will be deployed in conjunction with the PDT.

3.2.4 PDT Backend

In order to deploy and use this component, the administrator has first to download the source code from the project's repository.

```
git clone http://snf-877903.vm.okeanos.grnet.gr/pavlos/pdt-backend.git
```

And later compile the source code. Assuming maven 3 and Java 8 are pre-installed, it needs to execute the following:

```
mvn clean install
```

The component can be executed via a java JRE tools, but we also provide a Dockerfile to fully containerize the deployment and integrate it with the LXS datastore. Firstly, they would need to locally build a docker image. Assuming that docker has been already installed in the host machine, they should execute the following:

```
docker build -t pdt-backend .
```

This will create a docker image that can be found in the host machine's catalogue. To execute the component, a docker-compose file has also been provided in the GitLab, which makes use of the LXS datastore. The latter must have been already available in the host machine's docker catalogue. To start everything, the administrator should execute the following:

```
docker-compose up
```

The docker-compose file exposes the 54735 port to the host machine, where the servlet container listens to. Therefore, the administrators can now open their favorite browser and put the following URL, which will open the swagger documentation:

```
http://localhost:54735
```

An alternative option for starting the PDT backend is to manually start firstly the LXS relational datastore, and then the PDT backend. With the assumption that the docker images for both the relational datastore and the PDT backend has been already created and available, then the user needs to first start the datastore by executing the following:

```
docker run -d -p 2181:2181 -p 1529:1529 --name datastore --env KVPEXTERNALIP='datastore!9800'  
policy-store
```

Once the datastore is running, then the user can start the PDT backend with:

```
docker run -d -p 54735:54735 --name pdt_backend --env DATASTORE_HOST='172.17.0.2' --env  
swagger_path=/tmp/pdt-backend
```

Once the backend has been started, then the administration can still open a browser and check that everything is working by invoking the swagger documentation, as shown before at:

```
http://localhost:54735
```

4 Conclusions

This deliverable provided a description of the software components of the Policy Management Framework Layer and Policy Development Toolkit Layer, which consists of the frontend part of the PolicyCLOUD platform and allow policy makers to create, update and evaluate policies. For each component, a description of its APIs, specification of the main functionalities, and description of the source code is provided.

References

- [1] PolicyCLOUD. D5.4 “Cross-sector Policy Lifecycle Management Design and Open Specification 2”. Armend Duzha et al 2021.
- [2] PolicyCLOUD. D2.2 “Conceptual Model and Reference Architecture”, Panayiotis Michael et al 2021.
- [3] Swagger [Online], Available at: <https://swagger.io/tools/swagger-ui/>
- [4] Angular [Online], Available at: <https://angular.io>
- [5] Angular Material [Online], Available at: <https://material.angular.io/>
- [6] NGINX [Online], Available at: <https://www.nginx.com/>
- [7] Leaflet [Online], Available at: <https://leafletjs.com/>
- [8] Amcharts [Online], Available at: <https://www.amcharts.com/>
- [9] Apache Tomcat [Online], Available at: <http://tomcat.apache.org/>